

Providing access to cost-efficient, replicable,
safe and flexible CCUS

D12.6 - Neutral solution packages for CCUS implementation in smart, sustainable cities

ACCSESS has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101022487

Coordinated by: SINTEF Energi AS - www.sintef.no/energy

About ACCSESS

If CO₂ capture and storage (CCS) is to become a relevant, large-scale technology for cutting carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions, several barriers need to be addressed, and its deployment must be accelerated.

ACCSESS works to address key challenges to the successful implementation of CCS across Europe: namely, challenges related to CO₂ capture, CCS chains, and societal acceptance. The project focuses on four industrial sectors with the potential to drastically reduce CO₂ emissions by implementing CCS: waste-to-energy, pulp and paper, cement, and biorefineries.

ACCSESS started in May 2021. Its consortium consists of 18 partners from eight different European countries.

www.projectaccess.eu

Contact: Kristin.Jordal@sintef.no

Deliverable number:	D12.6
Deliverable title:	Neutral solution packages for CCUS implementation in smart, sustainable cities
Work package:	WP12 Societal integration of CCUS
Lead participant:	FHG

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Uploaded and Approval by	Date
Uploaded by lead Beneficiary:	2024/05/28
Approved by WP lead:	2024/06/18
Approved by SP lead (for WP2-11):	
Approved by PMT:	2024/06/18

Keywords
Carbon capture and storage, CCS, Carbon capture utilisation and storage, CCUS, implementation, replication, public awareness, municipality, city, public awareness, value chain, neutral solution package, NSP, Waste to Energy, demolition concrete, net-zero product, emission reductions, CO ₂ transport and storage.

Abstract

Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) and Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage (CCUS) are increasingly vital in urban sustainability agendas for their role in mitigating climate change. CCS focusses on capturing CO₂ emissions from industrial and energy-related sources and storing them permanently underground, while CCUS extends this concept by utilising the captured CO₂ for further applications.

This deliverable highlights the need for clear and factual communication with the aim to improve public awareness and knowledge around CC(U)S technologies through unbiased information, especially considering limited information regarding challenges and benefits of usage in an urban context; as retrofitting of industry plants, such as Waste to Energy, to use CC(U)S technologies near cities, or transport of captured CO₂ through urban areas. The deliverable addresses common concerns like the possibility of CO₂ leakage, technological failures, and mistrust in the incentives behind promoting CC(U)S, which sometimes are seen as a means of greenwashing rather than a sustainable solution.

This document introduces the concepts of Use Case (UC) and Neutral Solution Package (NSP) in the context of CCUS. UCs are detailed examples that show how CCUS technologies can be applied in urban context, providing practical insights into their implementation. NSPs, derived from these UCs, are standardised guides offering clear, actionable strategies for cities to effectively adopt and adapt CCUS technologies. These solutions are designed to simplify complex CCUS concepts, making them accessible to city planners and stakeholders, thus facilitating the integration of CCUS into urban sustainability and carbon neutrality goals.

Through the development and dissemination of NSPs, this document provides comprehensive guidelines for understanding how CC(U)S could be implemented in urban and peri-urban settings. It covers diverse scenarios and practical applications of CCS and CCUS, guiding cities in assessing the feasibility and integration of these technologies into customised action plans. The aim is to foster informed decision-making and public-private collaborations, ultimately driving sustainable, low-carbon urban development.

The deliverable also bridges the communication gap between technical experts, city planners, and the public. By using UC and NSP frameworks, it presents an in-depth analysis of CC(U)S applications, their benefits, and challenges for cities, as well as local stakeholders. This approach not only informs but, where relevant, also empowers cities to consider integration of CC(U)S into their sustainability strategies, thus catalysing a transition towards a more sustainable and low carbon emissions future.

In summary, this document provides a strategic framework for cities to understand and where beneficial implement CC(U)S solutions, thus improving their capacity to achieve long-term climate goals and promoting sustainable urban development.

Please cite this report as: Zhuravlova et al., 2024. *Neutral solution packages for CCUS implementation in smart, sustainable cities (D12.6)*.

Refer to the ACCESS community on Zenodo.org for citation with DOI (<https://zenodo.org/communities/access>)

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1 LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

CaCO ₃	Calcium Carbonate
CC(U)S	Carbon Capture, Usage and Storage
CCS	Carbon Capture and Storage
CDR	Carbon Dioxide Removal
CM	Corrective Measure
CO ₂	Carbon Dioxide
CPU	Compression and Purification Unit
DCM	Demolition Concrete Material
EEA	European Economic Area
EFTA	European Free Trade Association
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
EU-ETS	EU Emissions Trading System
FEED	Front-End Engineering Design
GCCSI	Global CCS Institute
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
IEA	International Energy Agency
LCA	Life Cycle Analysis
MEA	Monoethanolamine
NSP	Neutral Solution Package
R&D	Research & Development
RCA	Recycling Concrete Aggregate
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
SET	Strategic Energy Technology Plan
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats analysis
UC	Use Case
WtE	Waste to Energy
ZEP	Zero Emissions Platform

2 INTRODUCTION: DOCUMENT PURPOSE AND TARGET GROUP

Although many cities are actively pursuing ambitious climate goals through strategies such as improving energy efficiency, investing in renewable energy, and encouraging sustainable transport, it has become clear that these measures may not be sufficient to achieve carbon neutrality. In urban areas and their peri-urban surroundings, especially those hosting industries causing substantial CO₂ emissions, the integration of Carbon Capture, Utilisation and Storage (CCUS) or Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) technologies is seen as a possible component to address residual emissions that remain after traditional mitigation methods have been introduced (Shang & Lv, 2023).

A study by Ulpiani et al. (2023) analysed the net zero greenhouse gas (GHG) emission goals of 191 cities, which were part of a greater sample that included cities from Europe and associated countries, and found that approximately 45% of these cities, specifically 86 of them, plan to include technological solutions such as CCUS by year 2030 to handle residual GHG emissions. This indicates a growing awareness among urban policymakers of the that CCS can play an important role in strategies to meet climate goals.

However, the adoption and success of CCUS is highly dependent on public awareness and acceptance. In their comprehensive review, Tcvetkov et al. (2019) explored the public perceptions of CCUS, finding that a high level of public awareness does not necessarily equate to high acceptance, since perceptions of the risks and benefits, as well as personal opinions play a significant role. Concerns often centre around the potential risks associated with CO₂ leakage or technological failures, and most public attention is focused on the carbon storage component, rather than the capture and transportation stages.

Given that CCUS is an innovative solution that currently often relies on governmental support, which is indirectly influenced by public opinion, providing accurate and trustworthy information about CCUS technology is crucial. This ensures not only informed public understanding but also builds trust and support for CCUS initiatives.

Therefore, this document aims to inform the readers about CCUS and its extended impact in an understandable and clear manner, particularly focussing on applications potentially relevant for urban context. By presenting a detailed view on how CCUS can be implemented and its potential advantages for **city administrations and local stakeholders**, the intention is to encourage cities to realise the potential of CCUS to achieve their long-term climate goals. This document also seeks to foster public-private partnerships, crucial for the successful integration of CCUS into urban environmental strategies. To offer a comprehensive view of the role of CCUS technology, this deliverable includes detailed descriptions of specific cases developed with the help of the ACCSESS project experts from industry and R&D, that demonstrate the broader impact of the technology across the CCUS value chain. The goal is to improve understanding the potential benefits of CCUS solutions in smart, sustainable cities, contributing to a more environmentally resilient future.

Firstly, the application of CCS in Waste to Energy (WtE) plants is examined. This example highlights how CCS can be integrated into waste management processes to reduce emissions while simultaneously generating energy, offering a triple benefit for urban sustainability (waste management, energy generation, and CO₂ emissions reduction). Moreover, considering that typically half of the waste volume is of biogenic origin, if carbon capture is applied at a high

capture rate, negative emissions (as known as carbon removals or carbon dioxide removal) can be achieved.

Secondly, the utilisation of demolition concrete to bind CO₂ is presented. This approach demonstrates how urban redevelopment and construction waste management can incorporate CCUS, turning a potential emission source into a solution for carbon capture.

The third example explores the use of cement and steel produced with CCS technology in the construction, for example bridges. This case study shows how production of cement and steel, combined with CCS technology, can significantly reduce emissions in the construction sector, a major contributor to urban carbon footprint.

Fourth, the document addresses the challenges and solutions related to CO₂ transport and storage. This section focusses on the logistics, safety, and efficiency of transporting and securely storing captured CO₂, a crucial component of the CCS process.

Lastly, the document explores solutions for emission reductions in fuel production using CCS. This section presents an outline of what can be done to reduce the carbon footprint of transportation and logistics processes, an increasingly important consideration for urban areas.

Through these examples, the document aims to improve understanding of CCUS and CCS solutions, encouraging their adoption in **smart, sustainable cities**. By addressing these diverse and practical applications, the goal is to illustrate the versatility and effectiveness of CCS technology in various urban contexts.

In essence, this deliverable (D12.6) aims to serve as a bridge within the ACCSESS project, connecting the engineering-scientific community with **urban administrators, policy makers, stakeholders in relevant sectors**, to support their interaction with the **general public** and inform about CCS. It aims to translate complex CCUS technologies and strategies into practical and implementable solutions for cities.

3 Methodology: Neutral Solution Packages and Contribution to City Adoption of CCUS Applications

To address the objective of increasing public awareness and informed decision making regarding CCUS technologies, the methodology employs a structured approach using “use cases” (UC) and “Neutral Solution Packages” (NSP). The UCs detail specific applications of CCUS technologies in distinct urban or regional contexts, forming the foundational layer of information. Each UC captures the practical implementation of a CCUS process or technology, demonstrating the 'what' and 'how' in a particular setting, and is categorised into one of three areas as identified by consortium members: logistics (CCUS value chains), carbon capture activities, or the development of reduced fossil emission products.

Figure 1: From Technology Innovations over Individual Use Cases to NSP

Fraunhofer IAO and Institute of Human Factors and Technology Management IAT teams, drawing on experiences in sustainable urban development projects and collaborative project-internal workshops within the ACCSESS consortium, have tailored a UC template to capture comprehensive details specifically for the needs of ACCSESS project goals. This template gathers information ranging from the challenges addressed by CCUS, the technical and financial details of the implementation, the regulatory frameworks, environmental factors, and the distilled lessons and recommendations that can aid implementation and replication.

Filled out by consortium partners and validated through an iterative process of reviews, feedback, and clarifying interviews, the UC template serves as a detailed record of practical CCUS applications. This information includes functions, benefits, lessons learnt, driving factors, legal/regulatory requirements, costs, and financing options.

Building on this wealth of detailed data, the development of NSP aims to synthesize this information into a more standardized and accessible format. The purpose of the NSP is to help **city representatives** and **public officials**, to help creating a basis to better inform the **general public** of these technologies, and their understanding of the impacts and potential benefits of CCUS solutions with example of cases that have already been implemented or proposed. NSP distils the essence of UCs, removing location-specific details while maintaining the structural

integrity necessary to provide clear guidance for similar future projects. Within this course of action, where relevant, a Strength, Weakness, Opportunity, and Threats analysis (SWOT) is portrayed by looking at internal and external factors that can affect the decision making related to the replication of a NSP and implementation success. The SWOT analysis is designed to evaluate the characteristics of chosen case from point of view of a wider society and relevant stakeholders involved in potential replication.

The overarching goal of the NSP approach is to empower and educate city representatives with a robust foundation of scientific evidence and empirical insights derived from pilot UCs. The NSP serves as an easy-to-follow guide, providing step-by-step instructions on how to address challenges and steps for implementation, in addition to broad insights into the extended impacts along the value chain.

Data collection for establishing the initial UC templates was based on expert interviews and site visits. Then these templates were populated among the consortium members. Categorising into the three UC areas was a collaborative effort, with active participation from all ACCSESS partners during a dedicated in-person workshop during a consortium meeting. Coordination group meetings, two in-person workshops with partners, an online workshop and feedback sessions played a crucial role in refining the NSP methodology and ensuring that it met the needs of stakeholders.

The graphic representation in Figure 1 illustrates the methodology adopted by Fraunhofer IAO, which demonstrates the flow from technology innovations to UCs and culminates in the formation of NSP, thus bridging the gap between the engineering-scientific community and urban administrations.

4 PORTFOLIO OF SELECTED NEUTRAL SOLUTION PACKAGES

CCS is a way of reducing carbon emissions, which could be key to helping to tackle global warming. CCS constitutes a three-step process, involving: capturing the carbon dioxide produced by power generation or industrial activity, transporting it to a storage site; and then storing it deep underground in geological formations.

- Capturing carbon dioxide for storage: **The CO₂** is separated from the flue gases from industrial processes, such as WtE plants, cement kilns or paper mills.
- Transport: The CO₂ is then conditioned and transported via pipelines, waterways, road, train transport or ships to a storage site.
- Storage: Finally, the CO₂ is injected into rock formations deep underground for permanent storage, where CO₂ migrates into porous rock, situated under an impermeable layer of cap rock.

For more information about what CCS is, there is a number of public websites available, such as the Global CCS Institute ([GCCSI](#)) and the [Zero Emissions Platform \(ZEP\)](#). The ZEP website also provides an overview of what is on the political CCS agenda in Europe.

A curated collection of NSPs, each exemplifying a key application of CCUS technologies in relation to an urban context is presented below. These case studies were chosen to demonstrate the variety of CCUS applicability and its transformative potential for urban sustainability. Each case was chosen for its relevance to common challenges in urban environments and its potential for implementation in various contexts. Additionally, they are presented in a way that each NSP can be read and interpreted as a stand-alone document. For wider outreach and dissemination purposes the documents will be also published separately.

WtE Plants and CCS: Integration of CCS into WtE processes was selected as it represents a clear synergy between waste management and energy supply, two critical components of urban sustainability. This NSP is particularly relevant as it provides a solution that not only mitigates waste-related emissions, but also contributes to the energy supply of the city.

Utilisation of Demolition Concrete to Bind CO₂: Storing CO₂ in demolition concrete through formation of calcium carbonate. The NSP highlights the repurposing of demolition waste to sequester CO₂. It is a reflection of the potential of CCUS to turn urban redevelopment into an opportunity for CO₂ reduction.

Bridge Construction Using Cement and Steel from Plants with CCS Technology: Using cement and steel from plants with CCS in infrastructure construction, this NSP presents how urban infrastructure, using goods from two of the most carbon-intensive industry sectors, can be built with significantly reduced carbon footprint, thus guiding cities towards more sustainable construction practices.

CO₂ Transport and Storage: The challenges of transporting and storing CO₂ are universal to the deployment of CCS technologies. This NSP addresses a fundamental part of the CCS process that is applicable across different geographies and scales, providing a basis for understanding the logistics and safety considerations vital to the CCS value chain.

Emission reductions in fuel production using CCS: With the growing focus on the environmental impact of transportation, strategies for reducing emissions from transportation

processes are crucial, especially for cities with big transportation hubs and active logistics activities. This case study is relevant due to the increasing need to address this sector's carbon footprint and the potential for these strategies to be implemented in various urban contexts.

Each of these cases was chosen not only for their individual merits, but also for their collective representation of the spectrum of CCUS applications. They illustrate a range of strategies that cities can employ to reduce carbon emissions, addressing different sources of emissions and stages of the CCS process. Together, they provide a comprehensive overview of how CCUS can be implemented, offering practical and innovative solutions that can be adapted and adopted by city administrations worldwide to help cities achieve their sustainability goals.

4.1 Retrofitting Amine CO₂ Capture to a WtE plant

Klemetsrud WtE inside the plant. Image courtesy: Kinect Energy Group

About this document:

This document outlines a possible approach to retrofitting Waste to Energy (WtE) plants with Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS), encapsulated in the concept of 'Neutral Solution Packages' (NSP). The 'Neutral' in NSP reflects its design for broad applicability across diverse urban contexts, without being tied to a specific site. 'Solution' indicates a strategic response that effectively tackles the challenges in the given context, while 'Package' conveys the comprehensive and all-inclusive nature of the guidelines. Designed for city administrators and urban planners, the document serves to facilitate the understanding and adoption of CCS in WtE facilities, highlighting the critical role of CCS in driving urban carbon reduction efforts.

Description:

Retrofitting a CCS system to an existing WtE plant presents complex challenges but also an opportunity to reduce carbon emissions. WtE plants process substantial amounts of waste and can contribute significantly to urban CO₂ emissions. By implementing CCS, these plants can become significant contributors to CO₂ emission reductions.

Challenges/Goal:

The primary goal of this NSP is to highlight the complexities and critical factors associated with retrofitting CO₂ capture to an existing WtE facility. This will facilitate a better understanding of the risks and challenges associated with such a complex endeavour and

ultimately contribute to the development of sustainable and efficient carbon capture solutions in the WtE industry.

Challenges and solutions:

Retrofitting CO₂ capture to an existing and fully operational WtE plant introduces significant challenges, including:

1. Plot Area Restrictions:

- Challenge: Many WtE incineration plants are located in urban areas with limited available space for expansion. Implementing CO₂ capture (including processing captured CO₂ for transport) on site will require space. Height restrictions for CO₂ capture process components can also be a concern.
- Solution: During the early planning stages, it is crucial to consider extensive margins for the CCS technology. This involves anticipating not only the space required for the CO₂ capture and processing itself but also the space for construction and lay-down areas. Furthermore, negotiating framework agreements for land acquisition or lease before investment decisions can help ensure availability and control over the required space. Ideally, this should be done before moving into the detailed engineering phase.

2. Transport Infrastructure:

- Challenge: Securing the necessary transport infrastructure for liquefied CO₂ shipment by e.g. trucks or ships, especially if the project is located near congested areas or if the ports are not big enough for the required vessels and its added traffic, it can be complex and expensive. Although, the proximity to a port can be an advantage if the beforementioned challenges can be overcome.
- Solution: To mitigate this challenge, it is advisable to secure agreements for plots and transportation solutions, such as port access, during the preliminary planning phase. Waiting until the project is in the execution phase can increase risks and costs.

3. Coordination with WtE Plant Logistics:

- Challenge: The retrofitting of CCS can disrupt the logistics of the existing WtE plant, affecting the handling, maintenance, and safety systems of the waste trucks.
- Solution: Conducting a logistics mapping during the early stages of planning can help identify the specific needs and requirements of the WtE plant. Furthermore, future expansion plans for the WtE plant should be considered, as these can be integrated more effectively when CCS is retrofitted. Engaging in a master planning process for the entire plant, including the CCS, can improve overall efficiency.

4. Complex Groundworks:

- Challenge: Extending the plot for CCS construction involves extensive groundwork, including potentially disruptive activities such as blasting and excavation.
- Solution: To address this challenge, it is crucial to conduct a detailed front-end engineering design (FEED) study for ground works before the execution of the project. This study can help assess the scope of the groundwork required and identify potential issues. A survey of sub-ground infrastructure, such as utility lines, should also be carried out during the preliminary planning phases.

5. Efficient Use of Steam and Heat Recovery:

- Challenge: WtE plants typically produce steam and/or hot water from incineration for electricity and district heating. Implementing CCS can reduce the production of electricity and district heating.
- Potential solution: Address this challenge by installing a heat recovery system, such as a heat pump, to regenerate heat from the CO₂ capture process and redirect it to the district heating system. Evaluate feasibility, considering initial investment and long-term energy savings.

6. Power supply to CCS:

- Challenge: Meeting the electricity demand of CO₂ capture and processing may require substantial upgrades to local power grids, which can introduce delays and risks. It is important to note that a significant portion of this energy demand is associated with operating a heat pump for heat recovery if one is implemented.
- Solution: To manage this challenge, include design margins for electricity consumption in the FEED study. If the local grid cannot provide sufficient power, consider this a major project risk, as building new infrastructure can be time-consuming. Evaluating power grid capacity early on is crucial.

7. Wastewater handling:

- Challenge: Reducing the temperature of the flue gas before the CO₂ capture can lead to increased condensed water production, necessitating local wastewater treatment, which can be costly and space intensive. Furthermore, this water must undergo treatment at both the local wastewater treatment plant for the CO₂ capture plant and subsequently at the municipal wastewater treatment facility, incurring additional expenses.
- Solution: Address wastewater treatment requirements during the FEED phase, incorporating safety factors for flows, volumes, and footprint. Ensure that all necessary permits for additional wastewater volumes are obtained from local authorities.

8. Constructability:

- Challenge: Transporting large, workshop-built structures to an urban construction site can be challenging, often resulting in more costly stick-built constructions.
- Solution: Conduct an early transport survey to define the feasibility of transporting large components from the nearest port to the WtE plant. Evaluate the cost implications of extending the plot versus dealing with complex transport logistics.

Technology components:

Amine-based carbon capture technology can be used in WtE plants. This process uses amine technology to selectively absorb CO₂, resulting in a combustion gas stream with reduced CO₂ content. This captured CO₂ can then be transported and safely stored. To retrofit a WtE plant with amine-based carbon capture technology, certain preconditions must be met, including considerations for overall efficiency, minimising false air intake, and accommodating additional space requirements. The WtE plant must also be equipped to provide the necessary amine solution for the carbon capture process. The key components of a retrofitted WtE plant for amine-based carbon capture include the following.

- **Amine solution supply system:** Provide the amine technology and solution for the carbon capture process. There are currently several vendors in the market offering amine-based CO₂ capture technologies at the process scale required for WtE plants. The technology includes the flue gas treatment setup: comprising equipment for CO₂ absorption and subsequent release.
- **CO₂ Compression and Purification Unit (CPU):** Purifying and preparing the captured CO₂ for storage (or use).

Implementation Process:

Feasibility Assessment: A feasibility study of the CO₂ capture retrofit to the WtE plant is necessary to understand the cost effectiveness and technological feasibility.

Corresponding timeline for early movers based on interviews conducted with the relevant stakeholders:

Stage	Timeline (Months)
Feasibility Study	5 to 7
Regulatory Compliance Assessment	3 to 5
Engineering and Design	10 to 14
Permitting and Approvals	10 to 14 ¹
Procurement	10 to 14
Implementation Phase	12 to 24
Construction and Integration	20 to 28
Commissioning and Testing	4 to 7
Training and Workforce Development	12 to 14
Overall	60

Regulations and laws:

- **Environmental Permits:** Obtain permits for air emissions, waste management, and Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA).
- **Emissions Limits:** Adherence to emission limit values for pollutants.
- **CO₂ storage licencing:** secure licences for the geological storage of captured CO₂, this is typically done through an agreement with a CO₂ transport and storage operator.

Since WtE plants are often located in densely populated urban areas, additional emission permits are required. An environmental hazard identification and qualitative risk assessment have to be carried out, as well as risk and vulnerability analysis prepared. In the case of use of amine-based solution, there is a direct contact with the flue gas and thus emissions could get released into the atmosphere. To evaluate the risk related to amine emissions, dispersion analysis can be a part of the emission permit application. It addresses both air quality and drinking water guidelines, thus, assuring the environmental and health safety in the area.

¹ This is dependent on the country where the retrofitting takes place.

Citizen Engagement:

Effective citizen engagement involves educating and involving the local community in the CCS retrofitting process. This includes transparent communication about the benefits and impacts of CCS on local environments and emission reduction goals. The approach should aim to address common concerns, provide clear answers to frequently asked questions, and involve citizens in discussions and decision-making processes. Workshops, public forums, and information campaigns can be valuable tools for raising awareness and garnering support.

Advice for replication:

- **Engage local stakeholders:** Start by working with local government departments, waste management teams, and relevant technology providers. Collaborative efforts are key.
- **Site-Specific Design:** Customise the solution to meet the existing infrastructure and energy needs of our municipal WtE facility.
- **Feasibility analysis:** Conduct a thorough analysis of your local district heating demand, climatic conditions, and regulatory requirements. This will help you determine the most suitable setup.
- **Selection of technology:** Choose the carbon capture technology that aligns with the goals of our municipality, considering factors such as efficiency, size, and compliance with local regulations.
- **Compliance Assurance:** Ensure that the implementation is consistent with your municipality's waste incineration regulations and environmental standards.
- **Financial Planning:** Develop a financial plan that outlines the initial investment, operational costs, and possible financial support from regional or national organisations.
- **Community Engagement:** Engage actively with members of your community and local stakeholders. Building awareness and support for sustainable waste management and emission reduction is vital.
- **Performance monitoring:** Implement a monitoring system to track performance over time after implementation of the CO₂ capture technology is in operation. This will help assess impact on reducing carbon emissions and improving energy efficiency.

Addressed SDGs:

Media files and further reading:

Title	Author	Year	Link
CCS Retrofit Analysis Report	International Energy Agency (IEA)	2012	CCS retrofit - Analysis – IEA
Waste-to-energy technology integrated with carbon capture: Challenges and opportunities.	P. Wienchol et al.	2020	ELSEVIER - WtE technology
Modelling and assessing the integration of CO ₂ capture and waste-to-energy plants delivering district heating	Tuvshinjargal Otgonbayar, Marco Mazzotti	2024	ELSEVIER - Modelling and assessing the integration of CO₂ capture in –WtE Plants
Fortum Oslo Varme AS applies for the establishment of a carbon capture plant	Norwegian Environment Agency	2021	Fortum Oslo Varme applies for carbon capture plant - Norwegian Environment Agency (miljodirektoratet.no)
Dispersion and deposition modelling NO ₂ , nitrosamines and nitramines, for emission permit application	Fortum Oslo Varme AS	2020	Dispersion Report

4.2 Storing CO₂ in Demolition Concrete by Forming Calcium Carbonate

Image courtesy: [Neustark AG](#)

About this document:

This document provides a possible approach for the utilization of captured CO₂. Specifically, by production of recycled concrete with captured CO₂ by forming calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) from demolition concrete. This process is integral to reducing carbon emissions in the construction sector with help of Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) strategy, encapsulated in the construct of 'Neutral Solution Packages' (NSP). Maintaining the 'Neutral' descriptor, these solutions are universally applicable, transcending the limitations of specific geographic sites. 'Solution' signifies a strategic and effective response to these challenges. 'Packages' represents the all-inclusive nature of these solutions, ensuring a holistic approach to the challenges of CO₂ transport and storage. Designed primarily at city administrators and urban planners, this NSP illustrates how the integration of CCUS technology in the processing of concrete demolition can contribute to urban sustainability.

Description:

Demolition Concrete Material (DCM), as the name suggests, is waste construction material that is produced in large quantities during the demolition of concrete buildings and structures. Its use to capture CO₂ has become prevalent in recent years due to its high abundance of calcium cations and high alkaline properties, which could sequester CO₂ by reacting and binding carbon in the form of CaCO₃. This form is very stable, meaning that that the carbon from the captured CO₂ in principle will be bound permanently.

Combining CCS technologies with the construction and demolition waste sectors to store CO₂ by forming CaCO₃ has proven to be more sustainable than collecting and using natural limestone for new cement production.

Challenge/Goal:

With more than one billion tons of concrete per year, demolition concrete is the world's single largest waste stream and is considered harmful to the environment (Tiefenthaler, J. et al, 2021). DCM is normally dumped in landfills or illegal dumping sites, leading to increased pollution. This calls for recycling strategies for environmental sustainability, greener production, and economical reuse.

Furthermore, as urbanisation is increasing, with two thirds of the population expected to live in urban areas in three decades, the demand for concrete is estimated to continue to increase by 12-23% by 2050 compared to 2014 (IEA, 2018). As cement is a key element in concrete, the energy-intensive cement sector is also expected to grow, making it the third largest industrial energy consumer globally and one of the highest emitters of all industrial carbon emitters. The goal is to recycle concrete waste, enable permanent carbon dioxide storage in urban domain and reduce the carbon footprint of new infrastructure. This, in turn, contributes to the transition to a more sustainable construction industry by providing a solution that addresses both carbon emissions and waste management.

Solution:

A promising solution is the capture of CO₂ from biogenic sources by binding it in the form of very stable CaCO₃ in recycled concrete. By capturing emitted CO₂ from biogas plants and mineralizing it as limestone bound to the demolition concrete granules' surface, a permanent carbon storage is obtained, whilst simultaneously achieving negative emissions, as the source of the emitted carbon is of a biogenic nature. Then processed granules could be further used for infrastructure projects or for production of fresh recycled concrete (Neustark, n.d.).

Implementation Process:

The current recycled concrete aggregate (RCA) is used to sequester CO₂. For doing this, RCA is put into a tight reactor. Then CO₂ is fed into the reactor to generate a 100 % CO₂ atmosphere at ambient pressure and temperature. This leads to the reaction of cement and CO₂. The calcium carbonate forms microscopic structures at the surface of the grains. It cannot be separated. The RCA is then used as usual for mixing fresh concrete, as filler material in road construction or landfill.

Corresponding timeline based on interviews conducted with the relevant stakeholders:

Phase	Duration	Description
Initial Research	0-3 Months	Preliminary research and concept development.
Feasibility Study	3-6 Months	Technical, environmental, and economic assessment.
Stakeholder Engagement	4-9 Months	Engage with stakeholders and secure partnerships.
Design and Engineering	6-12 Months	Detailed facility and process design.

Compliance and Permits	9-15 Months	Regulatory compliance and permit acquisition.
Pilot Testing	12-18 Months	Validate technology and processes.
Construction Preparation	15-21 Months	Equipment procurement and construction preparation.
Construction and Setup	18-30 Months	Facility construction and equipment installation.
Testing and Commissioning	24-36 Months	Operational testing and system commissioning.
Full-Scale Operation	30+ Months	Start full-scale operation and monitoring.

Regulations and laws:

Production of cement that stores captured CO₂ by forming CaCO₃ from demolition concrete operates within a complex regulatory environment, particularly in Europe. Although a unified regulatory framework specific to this process is not yet established, the momentum of the European Green Deal significantly impacts the sector. This strategy underscores the importance of CCS and CCU technologies in achieving the net zero goals. Key points include:

1. **CCS SET-Plan 2030:** This plan outlines the advancement and integration of CCS technologies within the EU, setting ambitious goals to enhance these technologies for a broader and more effective implementation.
2. **CCS EU Directive:** This directive ensures the safe implementation of CCS technologies in a manner that protects both the environment and human health.
3. **GHG Performance Based Certification:** The EU is developing certification systems that focus on the GHG performance of low-carbon materials and carbon removal techniques. Such certifications could play a crucial role in validating the environmental impact of the CaCO₃ production process.
4. **Building Permits and Local Regulations:** Production facilities must obtain building permits from relevant authorities, adhering to local and national environmental standards.

Citizen Engagement and City-Company Collaboration:

1. **Educational Initiatives:** Launch educational programmes to inform citizens about the environmental benefits of capturing CO₂ in recycled concrete, highlighting its role in reducing CO₂ emissions and promoting circular economy practices.
2. **Local Government Partnerships:** Collaborate with city authorities to integrate this recycling process into urban waste management and sustainability roadmaps, flag benefits of recycled concrete for public procurement. This includes seeking regulatory approval support and exploring potential funding opportunities.
3. **Showcasing Benefits:** Highlight direct benefits to the local community, such as reduced landfill use, job creation in the recycling and construction sectors, and the long-term environmental benefits of sustainable construction practices.

4. **Industry-Local Collaborations:** Foster partnerships between companies involved in recycled concrete production and local public service organisations, e.g. potentially using the CO₂ captured from regional WtE plants, creating a closed-loop system.
5. **Transparency in operations:** Maintain transparency in the production process, including environmental impact, technological advancements, and safety measures, to build trust and support among the local population.
6. **Incorporating EU Guidelines:** align the project with EU guidelines and policies on carbon capture and use, waste management, and urban sustainability, ensuring compliance with broader environmental goals.

Lessons learned/ Impact:

- The described process enables permanent storage of CO₂. That means that even if the recycled concrete in which CO₂ is ejected is demolished, the stored carbon would not be released into the air. CaCO₃ is one of the most permanent ways to sequester carbon. Only temperatures above 600 degrees Celsius or very strong acids can trigger its release in the atmosphere.
- Storage capacity: currently around 10 kg of CO₂ per ton of demolition concrete. Depending on the specifics of the material, this figure could increase to 25 kg of CO₂ per ton.
- The technology is scalable due to inclusion of different actors in the value chain: by broadly deploying the technology at various sites throughout Europe, the possibility of operational cost reduction increases. Hence, the price of carbon removal and storage decreases.
- Removal efficiency: according to life cycle analysis (LCA), this CCS technology reaches a carbon removal efficiency of 93% over the whole lifespan (i.e., 7% of the CO₂ is re-emitted as grey emission).

Advice for replication:

1. **CO₂ source collaboration:** Establish agreements with CO₂ emitting facilities employing carbon capture technologies, such as biogas or cement plants, to maintain a steady supply of CO₂.
2. **Financial planning:** Develop financial models specific to concrete demolition processing and recycled concrete production, considering both costs and potential revenue streams.
3. **Regulatory Compliance:** Ensure adherence to environmental standards and seek certifications that highlight the sustainability of the recycled concrete produced.
4. **Community engagement:** Educate local stakeholders about the environmental benefits of this recycling process to obtain support.
5. **Market opportunities:** Identify markets for the produced recycled concrete, such as construction or manufacturing, public procurement contracts, to ensure economic viability.

6. **Best-Practices Documentation:** Document and share the process and learnings for global replication and adoption.

SWOT analysis:

Strengths	Weaknesses
Environmental impact: Reduced CO ₂ emissions due to the implementation of technology can contribute to environmental sustainability and compliance with emissions regulations.	Limited availability of high-quality demolition concrete: The availability of high-quality demolition concrete may be limited in some areas due to the lack of pre-selection prior demolition. Waste stream separation based on concrete properties is also required to improve the quality.
Reduces waste: This technology can help reduce the amount of demolition concrete sent to landfills.	
Produces a valuable product: demand for cement is predicted only to grow in the next decades.	
Threats	Opportunities
Insufficient availability of CO ₂ relative to the availability of demolition concrete.	Replication: The successful implementation of this solution can be replicated in other industrial plants, expanding the adoption of energy-efficient carbon capture.
	Environmental compliance: Meeting emissions regulations and reducing the carbon footprint can enhance the plant's compliance and reputation.
	Public-private partnerships: There are opportunities for collaboration with local governments, private investors, and technology providers to secure funding and support.
	Growing demand for cement: The demand is growing driven by increasing industrialization and urbanisation

The SWOT analysis of the production of cement that stores captured CO₂ by forming CaCO₃ from demolition concrete highlights a wide spectrum of key points. Importantly, it's worth noting that for city representatives involved in procurement processes, there are no relevant threats or weaknesses, as the production and demand aspects fall within the responsibility sphere of producers. Cities primarily benefit from the environmental and sustainability-related aspects of utilizing this type of cement in their construction projects. Additionally, effective educational outreach with citizens can lead to the city benefiting of public support. Furthermore, employing this type of cement in infrastructure projects aligns with the overarching objective of decarbonizing urban areas and economies, further supporting the city's efforts in this regard.

Addressed SDGs:

Media files and further reading:

<u>Title</u>	<u>Autor</u>	<u>Year</u>	<u>Link</u>
Application of demolished concrete material (DCM) in civil engineering structures - Review.	Mohammed Ali et al.	2018	researchgate.net
How our solution works - neustark	neustark	-	neustark
A new concept of calcium carbonate concrete using demolished concrete and CO ₂ .	Ippei Maruyama et al.	2021	jst.go.jp
The Chemistry Behind Concrete: A Comprehensive Look at Chemical Compounds and Reactions	Zaid Faridi	2021	Concrete Decor
Mitigating Carbon Dioxide Emissions in Cement through Carbon Capture and Storage	Nicholas Cramer	-	calpoly.edu
Technology roadmap: Low-Carbon Transition in the Cement Industry	International Energy Agency (IEA)	2020	windows.net
EU Policy and Support for Developing CCS	Maria Velkova, European Commission	2020	bcforum.net
CCS Roadmap to 2030	Carbon Capture & Storage Association	2022	CCS-setplan.eu
Recycling of calcined carbonated cement pastes as cementitious materials: Proposed CCS technology for calcium looping	Y.K.Kong, S. Ruan, Kiyofumi Kurumisawa	2022	ScienceDirect

4.3 Bridge Construction Using Cement and Steel Produced with CCS Technology

Image courtesy: Lake Pontchartrain Causeway bridge, [Mark Runde](#)

About this document:

This document provides a possible approach to incorporating Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) technology in the production of cement for bridge construction, encapsulated in the construct of 'Neutral Solution Packages' (NSP). Maintaining the 'Neutral' descriptor, these solutions are universally applicable, transcending the limitations of specific geographic sites. The 'Solution' signifies a strategic and effective response to these challenges. 'Packages' represents the all-inclusive nature of these solutions. Designed for stakeholders in urban development, particularly those involved in public infrastructure projects, this document aims to address the process and benefits of using lower fossil emission cement in bridge construction, thus contributing to the reduction of carbon emissions in urban development projects.

Description:

This NSP demonstrates the balance between the added costs associated with the implementation of CCS and the environmental benefits achieved, particularly in terms of the reduction in CO₂ emissions. The focus is on assessing how CCS, when applied to the production of key construction materials such as cement and steel, contributes to the final product, the constructed bridge. Understanding the impact on the costs carried by the end user is crucial, especially for public procurement in cities and municipalities.

Challenge/Goal:

Given the growing focus on corporate carbon footprint, the steel and cement production sectors face a significant hurdle in minimising their CO₂ emissions, particularly within the cement and steel industries. The incorporation of CCS technology into cement and steel plants has the potential to increase overall production expenses of raw materials. Manufacturers may hesitate to adopt CCS in their industrial processes due to concerns about potential economic consequences, decreased competitiveness of the product, and increased production costs

Solution:

With the use of low-carbon products, the overall reduction in CO₂ emissions can be achieved from the end user perspective. Low-emission materials can be a baseline for environmental performance for the construction industry and can have a minimal cost impact on end-users. The construction of a bridge made from products originating from a plant with implemented CCS can contribute to a large reduction in overall carbon emissions, utilising low-carbon cement and steel. The increase in the cost of bridge construction may be cost-effective for reduction in carbon emissions. To fully understand the possible effects of CCS adoption on end users, the costs and CO₂ intensity of relevant products must be evaluated.

Technology components:

Image courtesy : [Subraveti, S. G. et al. 2023](#)

Barriers to development:

Despite its promising potential, CCS faces significant hurdles to widespread adoption, including high costs, technical complexity, limited large-scale demonstrations, and insufficient financial incentives, and, as demonstrated in this NSP, bias toward expected high costs for the end-user and competitive place of products produced with CCS. In their study, Subraveti et al. have shown that using cement and steel produced from CCS equipped facilities in the construction of a bridge could lead to a 51% reduction of the greenhouse emissions associated with the bridge construction for a mere increase of construction cost of 1% (Subraveti, S. G. et al. 2023). Further results from ACCSESS project research show, similar conclusions: even though the costs for producing basic commodities can increase significantly (200% for cement, 75% for pulp, 230% for heat, and 6–37% for refinery products) when implementing CCS, the

increase in prices for end-users would be marginal (1% for railway, 3% for disposable baby diaper, 1% for housing, 0.4% for truck transport and 2% for airfreight). This leaves the basic commodity producer with the greatest risk when investing in high-cost abatement measures such as CCS and represents an additional barrier to the implementation of the technology (Emanuelsson, A.H., Johnsson, F., 2023).

Overcoming these barriers requires concerted efforts in research and development, technological advancements, and supportive policy frameworks that not only encourage CCS implementation, but also emphasise a comprehensive understanding of its impact beyond the plant and towards the end-user, as well as public visibility and demonstration of research findings. Cross-value chain collaboration and long-term agreements are necessary measures to distribute risk across actors throughout the whole value chain.

Enablers to development:

Enablers for the development of this case include the following factors: technological advances that optimise capture processes, reduce energy consumption, and improve cost effectiveness. Supportive policy frameworks with clear regulations, financial incentives, and public awareness campaigns can also drive the adoption of CCS. Industry collaboration, knowledge sharing, and pilot projects can provide valuable insight and demonstrate the feasibility of the technology.

Lessons learnt/ Impact:

- With the incorporation of CCS, despite a marginal 1% increase in overall costs of the end product, a substantial 51% reduction in CO₂ emissions could be achieved.
- The employment of comprehensive life cycle assessments to not only evaluate the overall environmental impact of CCS projects but also to discern the broader effects downstream of the plant where CCS is implemented identifies opportunities for optimisation.
- Encourage supportive regulatory frameworks, streamlined permitting processes, and financial incentives to promote the adoption of CCS in bridge construction.
- Open communication and results demonstration of results may lead to faster technology uptake.

Citizen Engagement and City-Company Collaboration:

- Prioritising transparency and open communication: Establish clear and consistent communication channels to keep citizens informed about the progress, potential impacts, and mitigation measures of the project.
- Public Education and Awareness: Provide thorough public education initiatives to inform the public about CCS technology, its advantages, and its drawbacks.

Addressed SDGs:

Media files and further reading:

Title	Author	Year	Link
Toward an improved cost evaluation of carbon capture and Storage from industry	Roussanaly et al.	2021	ELSEVIER – Cost evaluation of CCS from industry
Is Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) Really So Expensive? An Analysis of Cascading Costs and CO ₂ Emissions Reduction of Industrial CCS Implementation on the Construction of a Bridge	Subraveti et al.	2023	ACSPublications
20 years of carbon capture and storage	IEA	2016	IEA – CCS
Public perception and acceptance of CCUS: preliminary findings of a qualitative case study in Greece	Stavrianakis et al.	2023	EuropeanComission
The Cost to Consumers of Carbon Capture and Storage – A Product Value Chain Analysis	Anna Hörbe Emanuelsson, Filip Johnsson	2023	The Cost to Consumers of Carbon Capture and Storage—A Product Value Chain Analysis (chalmers.se)
Is Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) Really So Expensive? An Analysis of Cascading Costs and CO ₂ Emissions Reduction of Industrial CCS Implementation on the Construction of a Bridge	Sai Gokul Subraveti, Elda Rodríguez Angel, Andrea Ramírez, Simon Roussanaly	2023	Is Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) Really So Expensive? An Analysis of Cascading Costs and CO₂ Emissions Reduction of Industrial CCS Implementation on the Construction of a Bridge Environmental Science & Technology (acs.org)

4.4 CO₂ Transport and Storage as a Service

Image courtesy: [Northern Lights Project](#)

About this document:

This document provides a possible approach to establishing CO₂ transport and storage services as part of a comprehensive Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) strategy, encapsulated in the construct of 'Neutral Solution Packages' (NSP). The 'Neutral' in NSP reflects its design for broad applicability across diverse contexts, without being tied to a specific site. 'Solution' indicates a strategic response that effectively tackles the challenges of CCS implementation, while 'Packages' conveys the comprehensive and all-inclusive nature of the guidelines. The primary audience for this document includes policymakers, stakeholders in the energy and energy intensive industry sectors, and city administrators who are instrumental in driving the transition to low-carbon urban environments. Exploring the crucial role of cities in the logistics of captured CO₂, particularly through ports and river transport, this case aims to offer a broader understanding of the larger-scale processes involved in CO₂ transport. The focus here is on the pivotal role of the CO₂ transport and storage infrastructure in supporting a wide range of CCS initiatives, critical to achieving significant urban carbon emissions.

Description:

The essence of a CCS hub is collective transport and storage infrastructure that supports a range of different emitters, CO₂ capture operators and possibly several hubs to CO₂ storage sites. Transport and storage operators are responsible for transporting the captured CO₂ by pipeline, ship, or other means to the storage site, where they inject it into the subsurface geology.

Challenge/Aim:

The main objective is to assist industrial emitters in preventing unavoidable emissions from entering the atmosphere, and to provide a safe and permanent storage solution for captured CO₂. The main challenge here is to establish a CCS value chain within Europe with a potentially growing capacity to store CO₂ as demand grows.

Solution:

Projects that require CO₂ shipping by means of transport include receiving already captured and conditioned CO₂ from industrial sources and transporting it from the capture sites to an onshore terminal (for now in Europe: on the Norwegian west coast). From there, it will be transported by pipeline or specially designed ships to an offshore storage location and injected for permanent storage below the seabed of the North Sea. Across the entire transport chain, multiple modes of transport are possible depending on the specific chain (pipeline, ships, trains, trucks, or barges).

Within the EU's Project of Common Interest, European Commission chose 14 projects on CO₂ transport and storage, where in each project specifics of the infrastructure chain differ (Global CCS Institute, 2023). In the example of the Northern Lights project, that is part of the listed projects, CO₂ is transported by ship to a storage site on the Norwegian continental shelf. In its first phase, Northern Lights estimates to develop a storage capacity of 1.5 million tonnes CO₂ per annum. This will be done by developing an open infrastructure to transport captured CO₂ by ship to an intermediate terminal located in western Norway, to then be sent to its permanent storage located in a reservoir 2.600m under the seabed (Northern Lights, n.d.).

Implementation Process:

Image courtesy: [CCS value chain from CO₂ capture to permanent storage](#)

The phases and milestones of the CO₂ storage life cycle, including the various permits for the correct implementation of such a project, are as follows:

The first **assessment** phase includes the assessment of the storage potential, defining the storage sites and their related exploration requirements, followed by a review of the exploration permit applications. At the end of this phase, the project should be awarded an **Exploration Permit**.

The second **Characterisation** phase starts with a review of the storage permit applications, making sure that compliance with all requirements of the directives is ensured in consideration with the opinions of the Commission. The end of this stage is marked by obtaining a **storage permit**.

The third **development** phase is in charge of the oversight of any baseline monitoring & reporting necessary for the successful implementation of the project, coming up with monitoring and corrective measures (CM) plans, and approving of any updates related to them. Afterwards, the **injection process** may begin.

The fourth **operation** phase involves regular inspections, review of storage permits, oversight of the monitoring & reporting process, and approval of the monitoring and CM plan updates. Corrective measures must be taken if needed, and periodic adjustments to financial security are of great importance. At the end of this phase, two possible paths are identified: (1) Authorisation to close, which starts with the approval of a definitive post-closure plan (*circumstance 1*) or (2) Decision to close site after permit withdrawal (*circumstance 2*).

The next **Post-Closure/ Pre-Transfer** phase depends on the path occurring: *Circumstance 1* involves continuation of the inspections, oversight of the monitoring & reporting process, and the like before approval of the monitoring/CM plan updates. *Circumstance 2*, on the other hand, takes on operator responsibilities for monitoring, reporting, CM, risk assessment, and modelling, and **transfers the responsibility** for operation to the to the country where the storage site is located.

Finally, the last **post-transfer** phase involves long-term stewardship by EU Member States, which will be responsible for monitoring to detect leakages, for conducting corrective measures, as needed, and for surrendering allowances, as needed. Depending on the specific agreements, EEA and EFTA countries may be involved.

Implementation time required:

- Evaluation and exploration phase after receiving a survey permit: up to 3 years.
- Evaluation of the phase of CO₂ storage potential after receiving an exploration permit: up to 10 years.
- Development and operation phase after receiving an exploitation permit: up to 50 years.
- Shutdown and post-operation phase: up to 20 years.
- Transfer of responsibility phase: up to 30 years.

Regulations and laws:

The implementation of such projects must comply with certain regulations and laws both on the national and international level. The EU-Emission Trading System (EU-ETS) Directive 2003/87 applies so far to such projects as it sets the European Emission ETS, which establishes the scheme for greenhouse emission allowance within the EU. This directive is amended by the newer Directive (EU) 2023/959 of 10 May 2023. Furthermore, EU Directive 2009/31 establishes the EU legal framework for cross-border transport and storage of CO₂, which also proves relevant for such infrastructure projects. However, since there are only a few projects of this kind under construction in Europe (the Longship by Northern Lights to be operational in 2024 and the project lead by Porthos approved in 2023), regulations have not yet been adapted to cover all phases of the initiative, leaving loopholes and uncertainties regarding the responsibilities over possible CO₂ leaks between the different CCS value chain actors.

A good example is the Norwegian interpretation of the EU's Monitoring and Reporting Regulations, which states that carbon capture operators will be able to deduct CO₂ from their emissions accounts *once* it has been transferred from the CO₂ transport ship to the reception

terminal. The European Commission has agreed with this interpretation of the law. However, this implies that a carbon capture operator cannot deduct CO₂ from its emissions account before it has been transferred from the ship to the reception terminal and the storage operator has issued a confirmation of the quantity of CO₂ that was delivered. Furthermore, according to the EU ETS directive, the capture operator will not have approved deductions from its emissions for any CO₂ leaks during transport, suggesting that the capture operators are left with the financial risk of CO₂ leakage from a ship they are not operating themselves.

A solution to this problem could be found in additional bilateral agreements between carbon capture and carbon storage operators, which state that the carbon capture operator will not be responsible for CO₂ during the transport phase and therefore regulate the matter legally, as this particular subject is not covered by the EU-ETS directive.

Financial details based on a specific use-case:

Financial Detail	Input
Initial investment for implementation	Approx. 7 billion NOK (2019)
Annual operational costs	Approximately 250 million NOK (2019) Operation of 2x ship, operation of onshore facilities, 1 x injection well

Barriers to development:

With respect to regulatory challenges, storage liabilities are a key risk for transport and storage operators when it comes to legally defined responsibilities. CO₂ storage liability should be made clear in advance, answering the question of which party is responsible at each stage of injection, monitoring, and long-term stewardship. Regulations on how risk is shared and eventually transferred to government should also be included, and current regulations should be updated to include the non-ETS sectors.

Furthermore, in some projects, conditioned CO₂ is transported using trucks and ships in this CCS chain, while current regulations have assumed that transportation is done solely through pipelines. Complications regarding international cross-border CO₂ transport also pose a challenge: At what point is the responsibility for a CO₂ leak during transport transferred from one country to another? Bilateral agreements between the countries may be a potential solution here. There is also possible social and political resistance since there is ‘no guarantee’ that a project will be successful from a climate change perspective.

Regarding storage facilities, challenges may arise as the transport and storage operator will need to invest upfront to quantify the storage capacity and derisk it for potential customers (e.g., geological derisking may require shooting seismic and drilling wells. Upfront investment in derisking storage will make it much easier to scale CCUS hubs, but few policymakers have focused on this to date.) Transport costs and long-term storage options pose additional barriers.

Permits for the zoning plan, consent for pipelines, and offshore licences are needed. The operator will also need to identify the specifications (around purity and pressure) of CO₂ to be delivered to the transport and storage operator. Looser specifications make post-capture compression and purification cheaper for emitters, but impurities in carbon dioxide - such as water, nitrogen, SO_x, NO_x, carbon monoxide, hydrocarbons, and mercury - can have major

implications, such as corrosion, safety etc, for carbon dioxide transportation and storage infrastructure.

Therefore, these questions must be resolved before the start-up of any commercial CCS chain.

Enablers to development:

1. Government support is helpful in removing potential barriers to development, such as regulatory challenges.
2. Trailblazing new public-private partnership models and navigating a path to a more efficient regulatory process.
3. The government bears additional cross-chain risks related to the interface between the subprojects, it protects private partners from weaknesses in other links of the chain (e.g., if one of the capture projects were to fail, Northern Lights could find other CO₂ suppliers, or if Northern Lights were to fail, the capture projects could likely find a different storage provider without facing catastrophic loss).

Citizen Engagement and City-Company Collaboration:

Public participation is vital to the success of the CO₂ transport and storage project, with the aim of building community support, addressing concerns and ensuring effective communication. Here are typical strategies in more detail:

- **Information Sessions and Workshops:** Organise events to educate the public about CCS technology, its environmental benefits, safety measures, risks, and challenges ensuring that the information is accessible and easy to understand.
- **Stakeholder consultations:** Regular engagement with local residents, businesses, environmental groups, and local authorities to collect their feedback, address concerns, and incorporate their insights into project planning.
- **Educational Collaborations:** Partner with schools and universities to introduce educational programmes and materials on CCS, facilitating a deeper understanding of its role in reducing climate change.
- **Transparent communication:** Maintain open channels for sharing regular project updates, challenges, and progress, ensuring transparency in operations and decision-making processes.
- **Public forums and Discussion Panels:** Host events with experts, community leaders, and project representatives to facilitate open discussions, allowing the community to express their opinions and seek clarifications.
- **Online Engagement:** Use social networks, websites, and online forums to reach a wider audience, particularly targeting younger demographics, and provide interactive platforms for information sharing and feedback.
- **Feedback Mechanisms:** Implement various tools such as surveys, comment forms, or online forums to collect and address public opinions, adapting project strategies based on this feedback.

- **Community Benefits Programme:** Develop initiatives that offer direct benefits to the local community, such as creating job opportunities, improving local infrastructure, or offering educational scholarships, to demonstrate the project's commitment to local development and sustainability.

Lessons learnt/ Impact:

Regarding technical and legal aspects, attention must be paid to e.g., fish farms in the sea during dredging, filling activities, and blasting operations. Timely management of land acquisition is necessary to address additional requirements imposed by landowners, as their authorisation is required for building application processes if the land has not been acquired. Additionally, zoning plan approval is required before sending building applications. Additional considerations concern potential cultural heritage sites that, if present, may incur additional costs and processes. Another important legal information refers to projects dealing with offshore CO₂ pipelines, as they are also the subject of the same building application process as onshore construction ones.

Some organisational aspects worth considering focus on detailed timelines and stakeholder management, which are essential for successful project implementation. It is important to set up meeting series to inform before main application processes start up to get early feedback and implement regular meeting arenas under construction. Also, different types of application have varying handling times (e.g., one-step application or framework, and start-up application). Project managers should be aware that the consent application to may have a long handling time of approximately six months and is conducted in two steps.

Advice for replication:

For implementation of further CCS logistics projects, it would be advisable to work on increasing public acceptance for CCS technology, e.g., through education, and to develop new storage sites, including evaluating onshore options, to simplify transport and enable CCS projects for inland plants.

SWOT-Analysis:

Strengths	Weaknesses
Broad applicability: Serves various industries, enhancing versatility and market reach.	Regulatory gaps: Lacks comprehensive legal frameworks, leading to potential liabilities and uncertainties.
Advanced CCS technology: Using cutting-edge carbon capture and storage technology for efficient CO ₂ handling.	High capital requirement: Requires substantial upfront investment, making it financially demanding for new entrants.
Responsibility transfer: Transfers the liability of CO ₂ from emitters to storage operators, assuring professional handling.	Implementation Complexity: Involves intricate processes and requires significant expertise and resources for execution.
Climate change mitigation: Plays a crucial role in reducing atmospheric CO ₂ , aligning with global sustainability goals.	Tech-Dependence: Heavily depends on the success and reliability of evolving CCS technologies.
Opportunities	Threats
Climate action: The growing global demand for sustainable solutions presents significant	Public opposition: Faces a potential backlash over environmental and safety concerns, impacting public acceptance.

market opportunities for involved stakeholders along the value chain.	
Tech evolution: Continuing advances in CCS tech could streamline processes and reduce costs.	Regulatory changes: Future legal changes could affect the operational feasibility and financial models.
Policy incentives: Potential for supportive government policies, including subsidies and tax benefits.	Emerging alternatives: Competition from new, possibly more cost-effective emission reduction technologies.
Inter-industry collaboration: Opportunities for joint ventures with a variety of sectors, expanding usage scenarios.	Geopolitical challenges: Cross-border transport and international relations can influence operational dynamics.

In summary, while CCS offers immense potential in combatting climate change, proactive measures to address weaknesses, adapt to external factors, and foster international collaboration are imperative for its success in the evolving landscape. Ever-changing environmental and regulatory context is especially relevant for CCS logistics projects as they involve multiple countries with potentially different legislative background and conditions for operations.

Addressed SDGs:

Media files and further reading:

Title	Author	Year	Link
Directive 2003/87/EC establishing a scheme for greenhouse gas emission allowance trading.	European Parliament & Council	2003	EUR-Lex - 32003L0087 - EN - EUR-Lex (europa.eu)
Directive 2023/959 amending Directive 2003/87/EC	European Parliament & Council	2023	EUR-Lex - 32023L0959 - EN - EUR-Lex (europa.eu)
Directive 2009/31/EC on the geological storage of carbon dioxide	European Parliament & Council	2009	EUR-Lex - 32009L0031 - EN - EUR-Lex (europa.eu)
The EU legal framework for cross-border CO ₂ transport and storage in the context of the requirements of the London Protocol	Commission analysis services	2022	EU-London Protocol_Analysis_paper_final0930.pdf (europa.eu)

Transport and storage operators.	The CCUS HUB	Transport & storage operators, The CCUS Hub (ogci.com)
Long-ship carbon capture and storage in Norway's North Sea	Canadian Climate Institute	Longship Carbon Capture and Storage in Norway's North Sea - Canadian Climate Institute
Responsibility for CO ₂ in the chain	CCS Norway 2022	Responsibility for CO₂ in the chain - CCS Norway
About the Longship project	Northern Lights	About the Longship project, Northern Lights (norlights.com)
Porthos CO ₂ Transport & Storage	Porthos	Port of Rotterdam CO₂ Transport Hub and Offshore Storage

4.5 Emission Reductions in Fuel Production Using CCS

Image courtesy: [CEENERGYNEWS](#)

About this document:

This document outlines a possible approach to reducing fossil emissions associated with the production and use of transportation fuels beyond switching from fossil fuels to fuels produced from biomass. The description is encapsulated in the construct of 'Neutral Solution Packages' (NSP), where the 'Neutral' descriptor indicates that these solutions are universally applicable, transcending the limitations of specific geographic sites. 'Solution' signifies a strategic and effective response to decarbonisation challenges. 'Packages' represents the all-inclusive nature of these solutions. The intended audience for this document includes policymakers, stakeholders in the energy sector, and city administrators.

Description:

Transportation plays an important role in our global economy and is essentially provided through "vehicles" using fossil hydrocarbons. To reduce the fossil emissions related with the production and use of such fuels, biomass can be used as a feedstock to partially or fully replace the fossil feedstock in the refinery. The biogenic feedstock can come from various biomass resources, such as agricultural waste, forestry residues, algae, and energy crops, and it is important that it is sustainably sourced. The biomass can then be used to produce a wide range of valuable products, including fuels for aviation and heavy trucks. Some of the biomass is consumed by the refinery, to provide energy to the production process, which leads to emissions of CO₂. When applying CCS to biogenic emissions it could have the effect of net removal of CO₂ from the biosphere. This is known as 'negative emissions' or 'Carbon Dioxide Removal' (CDR). However, it is important to know that only a fraction (4-8%) of the total emissions related to fuel, from resource extraction to use in a vehicle, is related to the production of the fuel. The majority of the life-cycle emissions occur with the use of the fuel.

Billions of tons of cargo are transported around the world each year by trucks, planes, ships, and trains, accounting for up to 8% of global greenhouse gas (GHG) and up to 11% if warehouses and ports are included. Growing economies in Asia, Africa, and Latin America are expected to triple global demand for freight by 2050, which will double GHG emissions. Unfortunately, even today nearly all freight transportation runs on oil and gas, and with e-Commerce and home delivery growing further, freight will become the highest emitting sector

by 2050 unless strong measures are taken. A product value chain analysis can show both emission reductions and cost increases associated with a potential implementation of CCS: from the resource extraction and production to the use of the fuel. As in this case, emission reductions associated with production and consumption of fuels for airfreight and heavy trucks are explored; the aim is to analyse the impact that a reduction in fossil emissions from the oil refinery would have on the total fuel value chain.

Goal:

Efficient integration of CO₂ capture in refineries to explore how that affects emission reductions and costs along the whole fuel value chain (from resource extraction to fuel use). The goal is to reduce fossil emissions from fuel production. When part or all of the fossil feedstock is replaced biomass, the fossil emissions from the use of the fuel can also be reduced.

Solution:

Fossil emissions related to fuel production and fuel use can be reduced by applying CCS to the refinery and by replacing part or all of the fossil feedstock with biomass. Since the refinery only accounts for 4-8% of emissions through the whole fuel value chain, CCS has a limited impact on life-cycle emissions on its own. Replacing the fossil feedstock with biomass has a larger impact on reducing fossil emissions. These two solutions can reduce total life-cycle emissions of the fuel, from resource extraction to fuel use, by 3-23% when assuming that 20% of the fossil feedstock is replaced with biomass (Hörbe Emanuelsson & Johnsson, 2023).

Barriers to development:

Competitiveness of market prices: more costly compared to fuels produced without CCS and with fossil feedstock. Transparency along the value chain: biomass must be sustainably sourced to ensure emission reductions.

Cooperation and participation among all actors along the value chain are crucial to ensure the balance and prevent the production of lower fossil emission materials without market demand.

Furthermore, the majority of CCS projects today are economically challenged, with high costs of capture for dilute point sources and a limited number of revenue streams available.

Enablers to development:

Enablers for development, on the other hand, include the green labelling of fuels if they are produced completely from biomass, potential structural changes, and government support in the aviation industry, rising CO₂ prices, phasing out free allocation of emission allowances within the EU-ETS (for fossil fuels). The demand for negative emissions in the voluntary carbon market also serves as a driving force for beneficial change, in the case where part or all of the feedstock is biomass. If negative emissions are achieved, they could be sold on the voluntary carbon market, thus balancing the increased cost with implementing CCS at the refinery.

SWOT analysis:

Strengths	Weaknesses
Technology: The increasing availability of CCS technologies provides the potential to	Economic Benefits: Marginal potential for creating new markets and job opportunities in the green technology sector.

achieve CO ₂ emissions reductions from fuel production reductions.	
Market demand for sustainability: Growing consumer and business preference for environmentally responsible transport services.	High initial costs: Significant investment required for the development, infrastructure, and integration of CCS technology into existing systems.
Environmental benefits: A small potential for reduction in greenhouse gas emissions, along the fuel value chain.	Supply: Limited availability of biomass for fuel production, to replace fossil feedstock.
Opportunities	Threats
Policy Support: Potential for increased government support and favourable policies, including subsidies and tax incentives for the adoption of CCS.	Market competition: Competition in the transport industry, which may prioritise cost over sustainability in the short term.
Technological innovation: Opportunities for breakthroughs in CCS implementation.	Economic fluctuations: Sensitivity to economic downturns that can reduce investment in sustainability initiatives.
Expansion of carbon markets: Growth in voluntary and compliance carbon markets, creating demand for carbon credits generated through CCS, and, in the case of use of biomass, CDR.	Public perception risks: Potential for public scepticism or opposition to CCS projects due to perceived environmental risks or ineffectiveness.
	Regulatory changes: Risk of regulatory changes or lack of international consensus on CCS standards and carbon accounting, affecting project viability.
	Oil and gas producers: Countries which extract oil and gas conduct their activities at a rate which is not aligned with the Paris Agreement.

End of 2023, the 28th United Nations Climate Change Conference, the COP28, was held, where serious concerns about the global climate trajectory were expressed in consideration of the hottest year 2023, yet to be recorded. The final agreement in which parties settled on focused on a just transition away from fossil fuels and toward a green and fair economy, which should be further achieved ‘in a just, orderly and equitable manner’. Simultaneously, a call for tripling the global renewable energy capacity and doubling the current energy efficiency by 2030 was expressed, which includes the development and implementation of numerous zero- and low-emission technologies.

According to the Global CCS Institute, the COP28 served as an opportunity to reaffirm the importance of scaling carbon management technologies, such as CCUS, in a variety of industries, paving a way forward for innovative new projects in this area.

Lessons learned/ Impact:

Direct and indirect benefits that are identified:

- Only using CCS at refineries have a limited impact on fossil emission reductions through the fuel value chain since the refineries only accounts for 4-8% of total life-cycle emissions from resource extraction to use.

- The cost increase on the fuel when implementing CCS in refineries can be as low as 6%. However, replacing 20% of the fossil feedstock with biomass can increase the cost of the fuel with 30-40% depending on the price of biogenic feedstock (Hörbe Emanuelsson & Johnsson, 2023).

The key success factor is the importance of establishing cooperation and partnerships along the value chain. This facilitates risk sharing and aligns the pace of adoption for successful implementation, for example, by establishing so-called CCS hubs, which are clusters of emission facilities that share the same CO₂ transportation and storage or use infrastructure.

There have been several recent government funding calls for hub developments in Canada, Europe, and the United States to address industrial emissions and accelerate the development of both carbon removal technology, in the case of using only biogenic feedstock, and infrastructure. There are approximately 15 CCS hubs worldwide in various stages of development and many more are being planned.

Addressed SDGs:

Media files and further reading:

Title	Author	Year	Link
Perspectives on the Value of BECCS: The Cost of Bio-Energy Carbon Capture and Storage in the pulp and paper supply chain	Jonathan Klement	2019	<u>Chalmers University of Technology</u>
Supply Chain Driven Commercialisation of Bio Energy Carbon Capture and Storage	Jonathan Klement Johan Rootzén Fredrik Normann Filip Johnsson	2021	<u>Frontiers</u>
The Cost to Consumers of Carbon Capture and Storage – A product value chain analysis	Anna Hörbe Emanuelsson, Filip Johnsson	2023	<u>MDPI</u>
Freight Transportation	Climate Portal	2023	<u>MIT Climate Portal</u>
The world needs to capture, use, and store gigatons of CO ₂ : Where and how?	Phil de Luna et al.	2023	<u>McKinsey</u>

5 CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the Deliverable D12.6 “Neutral Solution Packages for the Implementation of CCUS in Smart and Sustainable Cities” presents a comprehensive approach to CCUS technologies in urban environments. It outlines methodologies for developing NSP, presents case studies, and addresses challenges in the implementation of CCUS. The document emphasises the role of CCUS in enhancing urban sustainability and reducing carbon footprints, highlighting its relevance in retrofitting WtE plants, CO₂ transport and storage, using recycled concrete to store captured CO₂, and emission reduction in fuel production for cities with growing transportation demand. This guide serves as a valuable resource for city administrations and public officials, advocating for the adoption of CCUS technologies in smart and sustainable city development. More NSP, based on the expertise and activities in ACCSESS are foreseen to be made available throughout the lifetime of the ACCSESS project, uploaded to the [project website](#) and the project community in [Zenodo](#).

The outlook for integrating CCUS in urban environments is promising yet challenging. Bridging the communication gap between engineers, public authorities, and civil society is crucial. To ensure widespread adoption of CCUS technologies, efforts such as those in the ACCSESS project must continue. This involves creating more initiatives that facilitate understanding and collaboration across these different sectors, ensuring that technological advancements in CCUS are effectively communicated and implemented in a way that resonates with all stakeholders.

In closing, this document highlights the crucial role of CCUS technologies in shaping sustainable and carbon-neutral urban future. However, the journey toward widespread adoption is complex, requiring a collective effort from engineers, public authorities, and civil society. Readers are encouraged to actively participate in this transformative process, share information and collaborate across sectors. Common contributions and inquiries are invaluable to bridge existing gaps and driving forward the implementation of CCUS solutions in the cities.

Fraunhofer IAO and Institute of Human Factors and Technology Management IAT are committed to continuing these efforts, ensuring the advancement and dissemination of CCUS technologies. The NSPs will be individually published online, serving as a vital resource for stakeholders in the field of sustainable and smart cities. This initiative is a step towards a more collaborative and informed approach to urban environmental management.

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